

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH SPEAKING METHODS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

Usarova Nilufar Yakubovna¹

¹A teacher of Kokand state pedagogical institute.

Mirzakarimova Muxbirabonu Ma'rubjon qizi²

²A student of KSPI.

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ANNOTATION

This article illustrates some beneficial and effective ways of improving speech skills. Moreover, it discusses the most high-priority speaking strategies during teaching a foreign language, mainly paying attention to the speaking section.

Key words: speaking skill, English, elementary schools, speaking strategies, innovative technologies.

Intoduction

Knowing a foreign language especially, English in the modern world gives a lot of opportunities to humans. It is just a vital skill, but also a kind of necessity. With the help of this skill, humans can communicate plenty of nations around the world as well as exchange new experience. English is also used as the first language in many countries or some nations use the English as second language. So, to be introduced with English as foreign language for the learners in Elementary School is the correct way.

Nowadays, teaching speaking skills is not an easy matter and totally different what it was several decades ago. Previously, educators had variety of dictionaries and textbooks with assignments in their teaching section. The learning process took a long time and sometimes did not attract students' interest. Step by step, the situation has sluggishly changed. Today, both of them, educators and learners are more active to take and give good effectively lessons. Today's generation is outstanding users of innovative technologies, digitalization of education.

Literary rewiev

One of the main target of learning English is teaching how to speak fluently. To make better and improve speech methods is acquired special environment, it is necessary to form suitable exercises and tasks to attract pupils' attention. Importantly, there should be separate lessons aimed at increasing speaking skills.

While learning a foreign language properly, some schoolchildren may face a bit issues. For instance,

- 1.Schoolchildren may be embarrassed to speak fluently, because they think “Am I speaking without pronounciational mistakes or unproper grammar notes?”.
- 2.In their early school age, the pupil mix the structure of constructing sentences.
- 3.The student may not have factual information in this second language as their own language.

Results

During the lesson, teachers must divide into various skills and parts of the speaking process like, begins new speech with common vocabularies, asking their interests into uzbek, then exchange into English. Firstly, each educator before introducing new topic, should work out all unknown words, repeat their pronunciation, write it’s transcription on the blackboard with highlight letters, and give their own example, depending on his life experience, for this word. In this case, pupils have more confidence during lesson.

Secondly, the teacher should give home tasks on the topics, covered students’ textbook. They explain with easily way and translate new words for them. Furthermore, while speaking, the teacher ask questions in accessible topics from life. In elementary school, these questions may include about school, their free-time, family maybe hobbies. There is no need to ask children about something abstract and pressing topics.

Therefore, it is crucial that, a foreign language is used not only in the classroom during English lesson, but also, the school department create outside the classroom language section. So, the problem is not dealt with teachers, but the skills acquired by his parents.

In addition, in order for learners to study English more sufficiently during the speaking section, the teacher conveys their lessons in an interactive way. For example, they need to deliver words to pupils, using colorful posters, numbers.

Conclusion

In recent days, we can see various teaching process. One of the most effective prepared resource is presented in a playful way. For this, the educator must select the most satisfactory ones in the learning stage. The most common ones I know, is ABC kids or Fun English. Because, one is colorful and effective app for kids to learn the English alphabet correctly, otherwise, for better memorization, words are pronounced. Another one, Fun English, it helps to learn new words and different expressions.

Confession

To sum up all, it is depended on teachers and parents maybe classmates, how to take and learn useful strategies. The most significant method, the teacher should

choose everything according to the age, interest, grade and level. The educator must interact pupils, also motivate them to see the new world and it's language

References:

1. Bulletin of the Tambov University Series. Natural and technical sciences.
2. Solovova E.N. Methods of teaching foreign languages: basic course.
3. Aitchinson, J. 1987. Words in the mind : An Introduction to the Mental Lexicon . Oxford and New-York: Basil Blackwell.
4. Rajapova, M. LINGVOCULTUROLOGY AND ITS PECULIARITIES AS NEW BRANCHES OF CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTICS. 2021.
5. Ahmadaliyevna, Haydarova Gulhayo. "Interpretation of the Image of the Heart in the Poems of Habibi, Charkhi and Sabir Abdullah." European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science 6 (2022): 621-626.
6. Ahmadaliyevna, Haydarova Gulhayo. "Talmeh or alluziya." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11.9 (2021): 772-779.
7. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳайдарова Гулҳаё. "НАВОИЙ ВА СОБИР АБДУЛЛА." ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI 1.2 (2021).
8. Rajapova, Malika, and Nodirakhon Sheraliyeva. "Teaching english through fairytales." Scientific research results in pandemic conditions (COVID-19) 1.06 (2020): 186-189.
9. Rajapova, M. PRINCIPLES OF COGNITIVE METAPHOR AND ALLEGORY IN DISCOURSE. 2021.
10. Rajapova, Malika. "BADIY MATNDA QO'LLANILUVCHI ALLEGORIK VOSITALARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI." Scienceweb academic papers collection (2020).

